

Responding to Policy Consultations

An *ekip* How-To Guide

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Responding to Policy Consultations

Introduction

This resource is intended to support you in engaging in public policy consultations and contributing to government policymaking. It is particularly intended for use by those in the creative and cultural industries (CCIs) who wish to share their perspective, expertise, and evidence with policy making, particularly around innovation policy that impacts them. These opportunities to engage in policy making may take place at a number of different levels – our guidance is intended to be useful at any of these levels including:

- International and transnational (e.g. at the EU level)
- National (e.g. Slovakia, Spain, Scotland, etc.)
- Regional (e.g. Bratislava region; the wider region of which Bratislava is the capital, Catalonia, Greater Glasgow and Clyde, etc.)
- Municipal and local levels like cities and towns (eg. Bratislava, Barcelona, Glasgow, etc.)

This guide is intended to sit alongside other forms of support, both general guidance on policy contribution and specific resources – for instance for many consultations industry bodies will provide guidance on key issues, areas to focus responses on, and data and evidence that can be referenced.

Why contribute to public policymaking?

Contributing to public policymaking offers several benefits, including the opportunity to influence decisions that shape the CCI's economic and societal contexts. Further, these contributions enable diverse perspectives to be heard, fostering more inclusive and equitable outcomes across the CCI and beyond. Engaging in this process enhances transparency and accountability with government, building public trust. It also empowers individuals and organizations working across the CCI to advocate for meaningful change, driving innovation and addressing critical issues such as social justice, economic development, and environmental sustainability.

Finally, as an individual or an organisation, these contributions can be an excellent means for distilling your approach to important policy areas, raising your profile and boosting your recognition as a key voice on that subject within your sector. In fact, distributing your position publicly following the policy contribution can be more important to your strategic aims than the contribution itself, leading to new connections, developing dialogue with other voices in the sector, and establishing your reputation. Writing up blog posts, holding briefings and presentations, conducting media campaigns, etc. can be excellent means for furthering your aims. For academic researchers, this could include writing a formal paper on the subject or on several combined policy contributions as a means for establishing expertise within an area.

What mechanisms exist to contribute to policymaking?

Opportunities to contribute to public policy vary widely. These can include (but are not limited to):

- Calls for contribution (sometimes referred to as calls for evidence.)
- Open consultations.
- Citizen's juries and citizen's assemblies.
- Invited workshops and focus groups.
- Expert written evidence.
- Expert oral evidence.
- Offering feedback on existing or draft policy documents.
- Offering feedback on how to simplify existing policy language.

Generally, members of the public are invited to contribute to public policymaking through these mechanisms via open calls (where a wide range of views are sought) or through closed calls (where specific expertise, or proportionate representation from specific groups of people, are sought.)

Not all parts of this resource will be relevant in all of these contexts, but you should use these sections and questions as a framework to support you in deciding whether and how to contribute to a policy consultation, and as you look at how to get started in practice.

This guide focuses on how to contribute to feedback through an invited process, where a government agency is seeking input on public policy. It is also possible to contribute unsolicited input to government policy – this is generally called *lobbying* (any process by which individuals or groups proactively reach out to government institutions, or individuals working in government, in order to influence decisions.) While lobbying can play an important role in policymaking, it is also a regulated area¹ that may operate differently in different regional and policy making contexts. This guide focuses on feedback mechanisms such as those listed above, although the information may also be helpful when considering other ways to communicate your perspectives and engage with policymakers.

¹ For example, EU guidance on lobbying and transparency measures around it can be found here: <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/at-your-service/en/transparency/lobby-groups>

Using this resource with the wider ekip policy engine

This resource has been developed for the *ekip* initiative, which is developing a 'policy engine' to support policymakers to develop innovation policies for the cultural and creative industries, particularly focusing on the development of open innovation ecosystems. As the *ekip* engine becomes adopted, there may be specific mechanisms, including policy corners, policy labs, and more applied testing of policy recommendations in regions, that may provide alternative structured routes to contribute to policy making.

If you are a CCI practitioner wanting to gather views from peer CCIs, or other relevant stakeholders, you may also want to consider using some of the *ekip* methodologies to gather views and potential policy recommendations to feed into policymakers or a response to a policy consultation.

To find out more about *ekip* and the *ekip* policy engine, approach, methods and resources, see: <https://ekipengine.eu/>

Before deciding to respond to a call...

Engaging in policy consultations and/or contributing evidence to policymakers to inform policy making can be a time-consuming process, so you should take some time to think about why you wish to contribute, and how it will be of benefit to you, your organisation, or your community. You also need to think about your own time and resources to take part in a meaningful way. Calls for contribution often emerge at short notice and have tight turnaround times for contributing: this section is designed to help you think through what resources and time you will need to contribute in a meaningful and effective way that will advance both your goals and address the needs of policymakers.

Questions to consider

- 1 What is this consultation looking at? Is it relevant to you?
- 2 When does the consultation, call for evidence or similar opportunity close? Is there adequate time to respond?
- 3 How important is this consultation to you and/or your stakeholders? What is the potential impact on you, your members/customers/other stakeholders?
- 4 How much time will you need to allocate to prepare an appropriate response?
- 5 Looking both at the requirements for the consultation, and your own requirements, do you need to respond to the entire call or is there a small but important section to which you want to respond?
- 6 What is useful to you as a person, or organisation or advocate to respond to which will forward your aims? E.g. do you want to do a separate publication of your own, showing that you've responded to the call?
- 7 Who else is replying to this opportunity? Would you be better off contributing to a wider sector / professional organisation / collective response rather than forming your own response? Are there benefits in providing a response specifically from you/ your organisation?
- 8 Are the timelines of the opportunity to contribute (alongside your normal day to day commitments and activities) feasible for developing a credible and worthwhile response?

- 9** Are there any risks to consider? Typically, anything submitted to a policy consultation is publicly available information: are there legal, societal or personal risks to you or your organisation by contributing to this call?
-
- 10** Where appropriate, have you checked your professional indemnity insurance with your employer (or the organisation/ group on whose behalf you are responding)? Have you checked that you will be supported should anyone complain about what you write or the evidence you supply?

By the end of this process, you should have a better idea of whether it is useful, beneficial, and feasible to respond or engage directly by contributing evidence to a policy consultation, developing a briefing for a policy maker working on relevant policy development, etc.

Practicalities: setting the stage for your response

Assuming you have decided to respond directly to the call for evidence or other opportunity to contribute to policy, you should think about the following practical considerations:

Questions to consider

Practicalities before preparing your response:

- 11** Have you read the call in detail? Have you read the supporting documentation provided? What is the call asking for and what will you need to do to address these requirements?

- 12** Who is asking for evidence? What is the remit of that department or committee? How can you tailor your response to address their specific interests?

- 13** Is the call attached to a specific strategy, piece of legislation, etc? Is there a white paper, draft policy document, briefing document, or similar background material you'll need to respond to?

- 14** Who should be involved in drafting and/or reviewing your contribution? Are there internal review processes? Do you have 'critical friends'² who might review and improve a draft? Are there key organisational or project partners, collaborators, or colleagues who should be part of the group developing a response?

- 15** What are the key points and takeaways you want to come out of this? Why are these the most important points and takeaways for you/your organisation? You might find it useful to consider what success would look like if you could make a change or impact on the proposed policy area or policy maker?

- 16** What is the level of detail or data you want to provide to back up those key points? This will influence how you make a plan for developing your response or submission and any associated literature review, research or data gathering to support your position.

- 17** Are there events, webinars, briefings etc that will be held as part of the consultation you can sign up for to find out more about it before responding?

18 Have you checked any technical requirements for submission, eg. registering for an online portal or submitting any documents via a website, to ensure that you will be able to do this in time for the deadline? (Tip: if the call is in an online form, copy the questions into a separate document so you can save your answers.)

19 What format is the evidence being collected in and which format will work best for you? Is it a report, is it a video, is it an in-person interview/event? Are there multiple ways to submit your response? Also consider:

Will you need design or other expert support (e.g. input on data visualisations, an economic evaluation, etc.) to make this work?

- a. Are there word counts or required formats?
- b. Can you submit data directly (eg. spreadsheets)?

20 What's the timeline? What are the key deadlines for submission?

21 What internal drafting, review, and sign off dates you need to meet these deadlines? Consider e.g:

- a. Do you need to build in time for a graphic designer?
- b. Will your response require sign off (internally or e.g. by a funder) prior to submission and are there any dependencies to bear in mind (e.g. planned annual leave etc)?

22 Is a branded/accredited document allowed, or does it have to be submitted free of all formatting, graphics, affiliations etc?

23 Will you also want to publish your response directly (if this is permitted)? And/or would you want to develop blog posts, editorial content or similar around your response?

2 "A trusted person who asks provocative questions, provides data to be examined through another lens, and offers critique of a person's work as a friend. A critical friend takes the time to fully understand the context of the work presented and the outcomes that the person or group is working toward. The friend is an advocate for the success of that work." Costa, A. L., & Kallick, B. (1993). Through the lens of a critical friend. *Educational Leadership*, 51(2), 49–51.

Evidencing your response: as an individual, an organisation, or an advocacy group.

As you draft your response it is important to frame who you are and why your perspective is relevant and important to the policy area at hand. In doing this you should explain in your response - either by way of introduction or in the framing of your comments.

Questions to consider

Depending on whether you are responding to a call as an individual or an organisation, there are different types of evidence you might consider submitting. We have broken the questions into questions relevant to everyone, to individuals and to organisations.

For everyone (individuals, organisations, companies, advocacy bodies, etc:)

- i. What makes you relevant as a respondent? What's the context of your response? What areas of expertise do you have that align to the areas outlined in the call? (eg. who you are as a person/ the size and scope of your organisation.)
- ii. What impact will the policy proposal have on you (or your members/stakeholders/customers etc.)

For individuals:

- i. You can give personal testimony from your lived experience, drawing on publicly available data where appropriate. You are unlikely to need anyone else to check this before submitting your evidence.
- ii. Will your response be more impactful as an individual responding directly, or will it be more impactful through submitting a joint response as part of an advocacy group, membership body, or collection of joint respondents?
Or multiple versions of this?

For organisations and advocacy groups:

- i. Is your response consistent with your organisation's position elsewhere? Have you gotten signoff from the appropriate senior leadership?
- ii. Do you get credit individually or is it a single submission as an organisation/body?
- iii. Can you back up the quality of the evidence you are submitting (eg. through data sets, testimonials, surveys, interviews, etc?) For membership bodies in particular this will be crucial: how can you prove that you are accurately representing the views of your members?
- iv. Do you need to cite information about your funders or any other relevant stakeholders in your response?

Evidencing your response: data-gathering and presentation.

Your response/evidence will have significantly more impact – and be more likely to be cited and/or influence the policy making process – if you can provide clear relevant evidence.

Data sources and data gathering to consider

- 24 Have you checked for existing policy and prior research relevant to this area?

- 25 Have you consulted with your audiences (if relevant)?

- 26 Is there time to collect new data relevant to the call?

- 27 Is there existing data you can cite eg. prior surveys of your own, or conducted by relevant bodies like government statistics, academic research, think tanks, industry reports, etc?

- 28 What data do you need to give a useful response? In what way will you be presenting this data? (E.g. can you include any data tables or illustrations? If not, is there any alternative for sharing this data, such as putting it on a website and including a link?)

- 29 Are there other prior responses you've submitted previously which you can call upon/reference?

- 30 Have you produced other relevant documentation you can refer to (eg. white papers, academic papers, surveys, articles in the press etc.)

- 31 Are there other policy consultations conducted previously (perhaps by other departments) that you can point to as useful in some way – perhaps even as a challenge to the way this call is being run? Eg. are there existing recommendations made by a different part of government that could be used by this part of government?

Writing up and submitting

Once you have familiarised yourself with what kind of contribution you could make, consulted any appropriate stakeholders (internal or external), identified your key arguments and the data to support them, you need to turn this into a suitable consultation response or piece of evidence to support policy making.

A checklist for writing up

- 32** Have you checked the brief and made sure what you have prepared is a good fit? (e.g. not veering away from consultation questions unless there is a clear strategic reason for doing so intentionally.)

- 33** How can you make it briefer? And make it briefer again? Policymakers want sharply incisive facts, but they want them in as short a format as feasible. Make strong, short points backed up by evidence where possible.

- 34** Does the narrative make sense, and is it relevant to the call? Is the story clear and backed up by evidence? Are the takeaways extremely clear? Is there a clear recommendation for a policy position and actions? This includes proposing an alternative recommendation where you don't agree with what is being proposed in the call for response.

- 35** Have you checked that what you're sending mirrors back the language and framing of the policy consultation/call for evidence?

- 36** Where is your executive summary? How will you make it clear in the case of an online form?

- 37** Who can review it for you to ensure you've met the brief and your response makes sense? Who is a critical friend for you?

Go forth and respond to policy!

This guidance, by no means exhaustive, is intended to prepare you for getting your voice included in the policymaking process. Policymakers value authentic input and evidence from those impacted by their policies, and whilst your comments or perspective may not always be acted upon, sharing your expertise can help to shape the emerging policy and your contribution may even be cited or specifically included.

By contributing to policy development, you help to ensure a diverse range of voices from across the Cultural and Creative Industries are heard, driving innovation and fostering more equitable outcomes for everyone working in the sector. Additionally, engaging in policy consultation can elevate your profile, build coalitions of trusted collaborators across many different sectors within and beyond the CCI's, and contribute to meaningful societal change for everyone. Yours is a valuable contribution to effective allocation of public resources and setting strategic priorities at all levels where policy is made, from your own town or region all the way up to the EU – make sure it gets heard!

Further reading and resources

Where to find calls for participation

EC: Consultations (no date) European Commission. Available at: https://commission.europa.eu/about/service-standards-and-principles/transparency/consultations_en (Accessed: 21 May 2025).

Contribute to law-making (no date) European Commission. Available at: https://commission.europa.eu/law/contribute-law-making_en (Accessed: 19 May 2025).

Engage in EU policymaking (no date) European Commission. Available at: https://commission.europa.eu/get-involved/engage-eu-policymaking_en (Accessed: 19 May 2025).

Have your say: public consultations and feedback (no date) European Commission. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/better-regulation/have-your-say_en (Accessed: 19 May 2025).

Have your say: Simplify! (no date) European Commission. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/better-regulation/have-your-say-simplify_en (Accessed: 19 May 2025).

Other mechanisms to identify calls for evidence and similar opportunities to contribute to policy:

- EU Policy consultations portal: https://commission.europa.eu/about/service-standards-and-principles/transparency/consultations_en
- National government engagement platforms and communications channels (e.g. in the UK open calls are shared via gov.uk emails, House of Lords open calls pages, etc.)
- Newsletters and email lists from policy-engaged organisations and member/representative bodies – who will often publicise open opportunities, workshops, consultations, calls for evidence etc. And will sometimes also suggest key data, key arguments etc. In support of their own position on behalf of the sector.

Some opportunities may also arise by invitation from government departments or through other member bodies, representative bodies, interest groups etc. who are gathering evidence to feed into a collective response.

Examples of policy responses

A Culture Compass for Europe (no date) European Commission - Have your say. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/better-regulation/have-your-say/initiatives/14609-A-Culture-Compass-for-Europe_en (Accessed: 19 May 2025).

Consultation responses & evidence-giving (no date), Creative Lives. Available at: <https://www.creative-lives.org/consultation-responses> (Accessed: 21 May 2025).

Cultural Policy Statements (no date) European Music Council. Available at: <https://www.emc-imc.org/cultural-policy/statements> (Accessed: 21 May 2025).

Evaluation of EU legislation on design protection (no date) European Commission - have your say. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/better-regulation/have-your-say/initiatives/1846-Evaluation-of-EU-legislation-on-design-protection_en (Accessed: 19 May 2025).

Policy responses (no date) Centre for Regulation of the Creative Economy. Available at: <https://www.create.ac.uk/policy-responses/> (Accessed: 21 May 2025).

Scaling up - AI and Creative Tech - Written Evidence - committees - UK parliament (no date) UK Parliament. Available at: <https://committees.parliament.uk/work/8502/scaling-up-ai-and-creative-tech/publications/written-evidence/> (Accessed: 19 May 2025).

Schmerber, L. (no date) *Policy brief on cultural and Creative Industries, Policy Learning Platform*. Available at: <https://www.interregeurope.eu/sites/default/files/2024-01/Policy%20brief%20on%20Cultural%20and%20Creative%20Industries.pdf> (Accessed: 21 May 2025).

General guidance

10 things to know about how to influence policy with research (2025) *The Commons Social Change Library*. Available at: <https://commonslibrary.org/10-things-to-know-about-how-to-influence-policy-with-research/> (Accessed: 19 May 2025).

A guide to working with policymakers (2024) *National Coordinating Centre for Public Engagement*. Available at: <https://www.publicengagement.ac.uk/resources/guides/guide-working-policy-makers> (Accessed: 19 May 2025).

Best, E. (2022) *Approaching EU policy-making*. European Institute of Public Administration. Available at: <https://www.eipa.eu/publications/practitioner-guide/approaching-eu-policy-making/> (Accessed: 19 May 2025).

Comparative Analysis of European Practices on Public Consultations (2021) *Council of Europe Centre of Expertise for Good Governance, Department of Democracy and Governance of Directorate General II – Democracy*. Available at: <https://rm.coe.int/council-of-europe-comparative-analysis-of-european-practices-on-public/1680aef56f> (Accessed: 19 May 2025).

Consultation in the EU law-making process (no date) *Northern Ireland Assembly*. Available at: <https://www.niassembly.gov.uk/globalassets/committee-blocks/windsor-framework-democratic-scrutiny-committee/useful-resources/information-paper-on-consultation-in-the-eu-law-making-process-13-mar-24.pdf> (Accessed: 19 May 2025).

How EU Policy is Decided (no date) *European Union*. Available at: https://european-union.europa.eu/institutions-law-budget/law/how-eu-policy-decided_en (Accessed: 19 May 2025).

IDEA Consult, imec-SMIT-VUB, KUL-CiTIP, Amann S. and Heinsius J. 2024, *Research for CULT Committee – EU culture and creative sectors policy – overview and future perspectives*, European Parliament, Policy Department for Structural and Cohesion Policies, Brussels. Available at: [http://www.europarl.europa.eu/thinktank/en/document/IPOL_STU\(2024\)752453](http://www.europarl.europa.eu/thinktank/en/document/IPOL_STU(2024)752453) (Accessed: 21 May 2025).

Influencing policy development (no date) *Community Tool Box, University of Kansas Center for Community Health and Development*. Available at: <https://ctb.ku.edu/en/influencing-policy-development> (Accessed: 19 May 2025).

Rutter, J. (2011) *Evidence and evaluation in policy making*, Institute for Government. Available at: <https://www.instituteforgovernment.org.uk/publication/evidence-and-evaluation-policy-making> (Accessed: 19 May 2025).

Stratulat, C. and Butcher, P. (2019.) *Citizens expect: Lessons from the European Citizens' Consultations*, European Policy Centre. Available at: <https://www.epc.eu/publication/Citizens-expect-Lessons-from-the-European-Citizens-Consultations-26c3d4/> (Accessed: 19 May 2025).

Thorpe, K. (2025) *How to engage with policymakers*, Institute for Government. Available at: <https://www.instituteforgovernment.org.uk/publication/report/how-engage-policy-makers> (Accessed: 19 May 2025).

Young, J. (2014) *Helping researchers become policy entrepreneurs*, ODI Global. Available at: <https://odi.org/en/publications/helping-researchers-become-policy-entrepreneurs/> (Accessed: 19 May 2025).

Thanks

The authors would like to thank Suzanne Black, Vikki Jones, Caroline Parkinson, Melissa Terras, and Vicki Williams for essential feedback.

We hope you have found this a useful resource and we would welcome your feedback on how we might improve and further develop it in the future. Please email designinformatics@ed.ac.uk with any comments or feedback. This resource is provided under open license (CC-BY-4.0) and we also encourage you to adapt, develop, remix, translate, etc. as you find useful – although we would appreciate you also letting us know if you do so we can also help share new or adapted versions.

Osborne, N., & McDonald, C. (2025). Responding to Policy Consultations: An ekip How-To Guide. ekip. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15592302>

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